

A STUDY OF THE IMPACT OF THE VEGETABLE OIL FROM COTTONSEED OIL PROCESSING ON SAFETY CRITERIA

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Introduction. Cottonseed oil is a cooking oil obtained from the seeds of various cotton plants, mainly *Gossypium hirsutum* and *Gossypium herbaceum*, grown for cotton fiber, animal feed and oil.

Cottonseed has a similar structure to other oilseeds, such as sunflower seeds, with an oily kernel surrounded by a hard outer shell; oil is extracted from the kernel during processing. Cottonseed oil is used in salad dressings, mayonnaise and similar products due to its stability of flavor.

Main part. Gossypol is a toxic compound found in crude cottonseed oil. Its anti-cancer effects have been studied for years and research continues. During processing, gossypol is removed from cottonseed oil, so there is almost no remaining amount in cooking oil.

Animal and human studies have shown that gossypol inhibits tumor growth and spread in some breast cancers.

Older animal studies have found that gossypol improves the effects of radiation on prostate cancer cells. There is also evidence that cottonseed oil can suppress cancer cells that are resistant to many drugs. An older study found that gossypol reduced tumor growth and slowed or killed prostate cancer cells.

Human trials suggest potential benefits for slowing the progression of some cancers, including gastroesophageal carcinoma.

Some animal studies suggest that cottonseed oil may reduce inflammation. Specifically, rats injected with cottonseed oil had lower inflammatory markers after a stroke-like brain injury.

There is considerable evidence that diets rich in monounsaturated fats can reduce inflammation in humans. People who eat a Mediterranean diet high in unsaturated fats have been found to have significantly lower levels of anti-inflammatory chemicals in their blood.

Inflammation is linked to chronic diseases, including heart disease. However, cottonseed oil contains only 18 percent monounsaturated fat. The Arthritis Foundation recommends other oils with anti-inflammatory properties, including:

- grape seed oil
- canola oil
- avocado oil
- walnut oil

Along with reducing inflammation, the polyunsaturated fats in cottonseed oil help lower LDL and raise HDL. It improves blood pressure and reduces the risk of heart disease and stroke.

A small study found that cholesterol and triglyceride levels decreased in healthy men after 5 days of a cottonseed oil-rich diet.

However, cottonseed oil is higher in saturated fat than other vegetable oils, which can have the opposite effect.

Conclusion. Cottonseed oil is high in vitamin E, an antioxidant that has been shown to have many benefits for the skin, including faster wound healing. Vitamin E has also been shown to have a positive effect on skin ulcers, psoriasis and other skin diseases and injuries.

This suggests that cottonseed oil may have the same effect, but that stronger sources of vitamin E can be found in it.

Unrefined cottonseed oil contains a toxin called gossypol. Gossypol has been found to have several negative effects, including:

- infertility and decreased sperm count and motility
- pregnancy problems, including early embryo development
- liver damage
- difficulty breathing
- loss of appetite

However, cottonseed oil is refined for cooking. The cleansing process removes the gossypol toxin.

References

1. "Texas is Cotton Country". Archived from the original on 2013-10-21. Retrieved 2013-10-23.
2. Jump up to: "Twenty Facts About Cottonseed Oil from cotton plant". National Cottonseed Products Association. Archived from the original on 2015-10-17.
3. "Basic Report: 04502, Oil, cottonseed, salad or cooking". United States Department of Agriculture. Archived from the original on August 24, 2012.
4. "Nutrient data for 04702, Oil, industrial, cottonseed, fully hydrogenated". United States Department of Agriculture. Archived from the original on 2013-09-05. Retrieved 2012-02-13.
5. Jump up to: Jones, Lynn A.; King, C. Clay (1996). "Cottonseed oil". In Y. H. Hui (ed.). *Bailey's Industrial Oil and Fat Products, Edible Oil and Fat Products: Oils and Oilseeds*. New York: Wiley. ISBN 978-0-471-59426-0.

6. Абашева, Е. А., Бабамуратов, Б. Э., Баубекова, Г. Д., Бейсембаев, Г. Б., Беришева, Л. Б., Булатбаева, К. Н., ... & Юнусов, Э. Ш. (2021). ИННОВАЦИОННОЕ РАЗВИТИЕ НАУКИ И ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ.
7. Yatsu, L. Y.; Jacks, T. J.; Hensarling, T. (1970). "Research abstract: Southern Regional Research Laboratory". Journal of the American Oil Chemists' Society. **47** (2): 73–74. doi:10.1007/BF02541462. S2CID 84360576.